

THE ROAD TO THE SECOND WORLD WAR. ROMANIA AND THE COLLAPSE OF THE REGIONAL SYSTEM OF ALLIANCES

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Abstract

During the challenging inter-war years, Romania played an active diplomatic role seeking to secure its borders and help building a credible regional security configuration aiming at protecting the Versailles status-quo order. Bucharest's main efforts focused on establishing, under the Western-security umbrella, a broad network of regional alliances so that to create a counterbalance against the potential revisionist European hegemonies. Nevertheless, the overall strategy followed by Romania failed due to rapidly changing geopolitical dynamics among the great systemic powers and the inability of the regional actors to harmonize their strategic agendas and security interests.

Keywords: *World War 2, Romania, regional system of alliances, Treaty of Versailles, interwar period*

With the end of the First World War, Romania found itself into a new security paradigm. The Paris Peace Treaties of 1919-1920 settled a new territorial configuration that allowed it to fulfill its historical aspirations of national unification, by bringing Bessarabia, Transylvania and Bukovina back to homeland. As a result, Romania more than doubled its pre-war size and population from 138,000 square kilometers to 295,049 square kilometers, while population increased from 7.5 million people to 15.5 million, which, by 1938, has already reached 18 million, making Romania the 8th largest country of Europe (Otu, 2006:21). Since the beginning, the settlement reached contained potential seed of further territorial disputes with its revisionist neighbors and this was to become the major security concern for the new Roma-

nian state that profoundly shaped its security and defense agenda. Against this background, Bucharest sought to forge a comprehensive strategy focused on building a dynamic security geography of regional alliances closely connected to the Western (French)-backed collective security system considered as the most credible option to manage the complicated geopolitical realities and preserve the regional territorial status-quo.

Romania struggled – during the challenging inter-war years – to implement its strategic vision and play an active role in designing a new power equation on the Eastern European frontier. However, in less than 25 years since its historical unification, Romania found itself alone (after France surrendered in June 1940) facing the Soviet threat and the German mili-

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tary might, loosing about a half of its territory, being forced to turn against its Western allies and watching its whole system of regional alliances collapsing.

To what extent the system of regional alliances could provide a viable mechanism of managing the regional strategic realities? Did the decisions makers in Bucharest – and if they did, to what extent – correctly assess the changing regional dynamics and the inevitability of the war? Could Romania make different strategic choices? Where there missed strategic opportunities or Romania was just another victim of the continental power politics that it could not prevent or manage by itself?

The paper will seek to provide answers to these challenging questions and bring new lights on a highly complicated chapter of Romania's history, one which paved the way for Romania's entry into the Second World War.

The Versailles order – a vulnerable security geography in Eastern Europe

The systemic configuration emerged following the end of the First World War was best described as liberal order 1.0 that was defined in terms of self-determination and the building of an international legal order based on the respect of state sovereignty, non-intervention, collective problem solving and the role of international institutions (Ikenberry, 2009: 71). The main pillars of the new strategic setting were grounded in the Western (French-British) status-quo commitments and the creation of the League of Nations, as the main body responsible of guarding the Versailles territorial architecture and of shaping a specific non-ag-

gressive way of conduct among the member countries. The rationale behind the new strategic vision was to be found in the Wilsonian belief that the power politics logic could be replaced with collective security and shared common security interests.

Despite the initial expectations, the *realpolitik* remained the main feature that shaped the structure of the European system of states so that the regional relations could not escape the logic of balance of power and power politics leading to centrifugal dynamics that dramatically weaken the overall Versailles system and left the new independent states from Central and Eastern Europe in a state of deep security vacuum.

The Versailles liberal order left a number of issues unsolved that were to become major sources of vulnerability for the newly emerged Central-Eastern European security architecture. Firstly, the main aim of the Western victorious powers was to create a ring of Western-oriented pro-status-quo states by maximizing the size and strength of four states: Poland, Romania, Czechoslovakia and Yugoslavia. This was intended to transform them into stronger and more dependable 'bulwarks' not only against any potential revival of 'revanchism' of the Europe's defeated states (Germany, Austria, Hungary and Bulgaria), but also against Soviet Communism (Bideleux, Jeffries, 2007: 322, 329). This division between revisionist and non-revisionist states was to be a fundamental weakness of the new order and profoundly affected the geopolitical dynamics within the region (R.J. Crampton, 1997: 37). Secondly, by dividing the former Habsburg territories be-

Johannes Bell signs the Treaty of Versailles in the Hall of Mirrors, June 1919

tween seven small and medium-size countries, it further enhanced the strength of Germany and made them vulnerable to Berlin's geopolitical maneuvers. Thirdly, despite the territorial gains, the new successor states were in fact economically, psychologically and strategically 'dependent' on the Western Powers, which became the main guarantors of their security by acting as a protection shield against the likely revisionist claims of the defeated states (Bideleux, Jeffries, 2007:328). Fourthly, the exclusion of Germany and Soviet Russia from the new regional power configuration generated a new balance of power in Central and Eastern Europe, whose stability depended on the Western (particularly on France) ability to manage the complicated regional games and to moderate the regional competing agendas. Moreover, the isolationist policy adopted by the United States and its retreat from the European geopolitical affairs was another key vector which deepened the strategic disequilibrium of the Versailles security order.

Strategic imperatives and regional solutions

Once the national project of United Romania was accomplished, Bucharest had to manage a complicated strategic equation generated by the growing security vulnerabilities of its new borders. The revisionist claims of its neighbors were expected to emerge on three main directions: the Western direction (the claims of Hungary over Transylvania), the Southern direction (the dispute with Bulgaria over the Southern Dobruja) and the Eastern direction (the Soviet Union's claims regarding Bessarabia and Bukovina).

Within the new geopolitical configuration, the foreign and security policy of Romania was focused on two main inter-related objectives: to preserve the newly emerged Versailles systemic order and to secure the country's territorial integrity. As a result, Romania's agenda developed on two main coordinates: firstly, it sought to forge a privileged and strong alliance with the Western countries, primarily with France and Great Britain; secondly, it assumed an active role inside the League of Nations seen as the main instrument of preserving the territorial status-quo. Within these strategic

parameters, Bucharest launched an ample diplomatic "offensive" of establishing a multi-tier network of security and military relations with its regional status-quo partners as to create a common front to deter the potential regional revisionist policies.

Immediately after the end of the war, the idea of creating a regional block of status-quo states was embraced by Bucharest as a top priority of its diplomacy. The rationales were twofold. On one hand, the regional actors could actively contribute to the international efforts of maintaining the Versailles systemic design unchanged and keep the Western powers involved in the regional affairs. On the other hand, it was obvious that the status-quo regional states individually did not have the capabilities to manage the geopolitics of the region which still remained in the shadow of German-Soviet hegemonic ambitions. Romania's main concern was to avoid being isolated either by the Western potential withdrawal to their "comfort zone" or by letting the main defeated powers (Germany and Soviet Russia) to use in their own interest the territorial disputes between the regional actors turning one against the other and bringing them under their influence and control.

It's worth mentioning that the regional diplomatic initiatives launched by early '20s were part of a broader strategic agenda envisaged by the Western powers, particularly important being the role of France, to redraw the balance of power in Eastern Europe. According to the strategic equation designed inside Paris political 'laboratories', Romania alongside the other newly emerged independent states – Poland, Czechoslovakia and Yugoslavia – was to play a key role in establishing a French-led system of alliances having threefold goals: to act as a buffer against a potential German revisionisms and Bolshevik influence, to strengthen France's continental hegemony, and to avoid a security vacuum in Eastern Europe that could "encourage" the revival of German-Soviet hegemonic game. This was to provide a favorable geopolitical constellation of interests between the Western "guarantors" and their small Eastern allies laying the foundation of a new security geometry seen both as a shield in face of the re-emergence of great power competition

and a platform of enhancing strategic posture of the regional actors *vis-à-vis* de hegemonic powers.

Romania within the equation of regional alliances

Even since 1918, Romania raised the issue of a regional arrangement to bring together the states from Central and Eastern Europe, an idea further developed by the Romanian minister of Foreign Affairs Take Ionescu in August 1920 (Popisteanu, 1971: 61-63). The security matrix imagined by the Romanian diplomat was to establish an "autonomous block" (Ionescu, 1993: 44-46) shaped as a defensive alliance among the countries from the Ponto-Baltic isthmus that was to include Czechoslovakia, Romania, Poland, Yugoslavia and Greece (Campus, 1993: 42-43). The growing antagonism among some of the potential members that involved disputes over territory or the minorities' issue generated new fault lines within the regional architecture (the divergences between Poland and Czechoslovakia or Greece and Yugoslavia are revealing examples) and made difficult the implementation of the Romanian plan.

Despite the initial failure, between 1921 and 1934, Romania's diplomacy actively contributed to the establishment of a broad ring of bilateral and multilateral alliances that profoundly shaped its overall security paradigm and typology of behavior in the aftermath of the First World War.

In 1921, Romania, Czechoslovakia and Yugoslavia established the first regional collective alliance called Little Entente in a common effort to resist the Hungarian revisionist aspirations as well as attempts at restoration of Habsburg Monarchy in the Danube region¹. The new regional structure was based upon a network of bilateral political and military treaties: between Czechoslovakia and Yugoslavia (August 14, 1920); Czechoslovakia and Romania (April 23, 1921); and Romania and Yugoslavia (June 7, 1921) (Haleki, 1980: 464). The political agreements were doubled by bilateral military accords that were to be integrated into a unitary defense vision so that on September 14, 1923, the trilateral military convention was concluded. The military document settled the obligations of mutual defense in case that

one of the signatory states might be subject of a military aggression. Basically, the military conventions of the Little Entente considered a common action of all member countries against an attack from Hungary; a common Romanian-Yugoslavian action to contain a possible attack from Bulgaria, and a joint action against a simultaneous attack of both Hungary and Bulgaria. The regional alliance was gradually strengthened and on February 16, 1933 an ample reorganization process took place leading to the creation of new permanent structures: the Permanent Council, the Economic Council and the Permanent Secretariat.

From Bucharest's perspective, the new regional alignment was to act as an important vector of securing its Western and Southern borders by deterring the potential aggressive moves from Hungary and Bulgaria.

However, Bucharest's main concern focused on its Eastern border which remained highly exposed to Soviet potential revisionist actions against Bessarabia. For this purpose, on March 3, 1921, Romania signed the military treaty with Poland that was to become one of the most important features of Romania's security policy during the inter-war period². The Romanian-Polish treaty explicitly mentioned that the two countries assume mutual defense obligations against an attack coming from the East. This was the only regional treaty reached by Romania that guaranteed defense support in case of a Soviet attack.

Romania acknowledged that the credibility of the regional initiatives depended on the Western defense commitments, particularly on France's willingness to play the role of continental hegemon. Following this logic, Bucharest energetically advocated and tried, unsuccessfully, to convince France to conclude a mutual assistance pact with the Little Entente as a way to increase the value of the regional arrangement and keep Paris as a key player within the regional power game. France's strategic considerations started from different assumptions. Its main concern was to contain a potential German geopolitical revival and prevent the possibility of a German-Russian rapprochement (Graig and Gilbert, 1995: 115). In this direction, the strategy pursued by Paris aimed primarily at consolidating

a line of defense around the German borders (this explained the conclusion of the mutual assistance treaties with Poland in 1921 and Czechoslovakia in 1924, but not with Romania) and at keeping its options open and not to compromise the links with the Soviet Russia and Italy that could have helped it to accommodate unexpected geopolitical developments and check the German ambitions. Therefore, Paris showed reluctance in developing a concrete military cooperation with the Little Entente as a whole and rather preferred to build selective defense agreements on an individual-basis. The treaty of friendship and non-aggression with France was signed on July 10, 1926 but, regardless the previous treaties with Poland and Czechoslovakia, it was merely a political document without mutual defense provisions and of a little military practical value (Hitchins, 1994: 455-456; Scurtu, 1995: 499; Hillgruber, 1994: 38).

At the same time, Romania launched a series of diplomatic initiatives to convince Italy to ratify the Bessarabia protocol of October 28, 1920 (*Treaty between the Principal Allied Powers and Romania respecting Bessarabia*), the only international document that recognized the allegiance of Bessarabia territory to Romania. The treaty with Italy was signed on September 16, 1926 and allowed Romania to enhance its posture in the internationally legally dispute with the Soviet Union over the Bessarabian issue.

Romania's overall system of regional alliances was completed through the establishment of the Balkan Entente on February 9, 1934. The new regional construction was established as a mutual defense agreement between Greece, Yugoslavia, Romania and Turkey and intended to maintain the status-quo in the region and guarantee the signatories' territorial integrity against attack by another Balkan state³.

Between 1936 and 1938, the military conventions were concluded, first the tripartite military convention between Romania, Yugoslavia and Turkey (Belgrade, November 28, 1934) followed by the quadripartite convention (Bucharest, November 9, 1934)⁴. According to the conventions' provisions, the member countries committed to provide each other support in the event of a regional con-

flict with the involvement, individually or in cooperation, of Bulgaria, Hungary and Albania. From Bucharest's perspective, the strategic significance of the Balkan alliance was obvious: on one hand, it was to provide a new securing line of defense against the Bulgarian and Hungarian revisionism and, on the other hand, it could allow strategic access to the Greek port facilities in Mediterranean in case that the Black Sea would have been blocked due to a generalized conflict.

The vulnerabilities of Romania's regional strategy

Theoretically, in the mid '30s, Romania found itself in the strongest strategic posture. It succeeded to build a security belt around its frontiers that allowed it to secure its borders on all vulnerable directions: in the East – the treaty with Poland, in the West – through the Little Entente and in the South – through the Balkan Pact. The treaty with France anchored Romania to what was considered the most credible security umbrella that was to provide a reliable guarantee for the preservation of the regional territorial status-quo and a shield against any revisionist attempt.

In reality, since the beginning, the network of relations imagined by Bucharest bore signs of weakness from inside since it could not harmonize or accommodate the security interests of the main regional players.

A few considerations are revealing to explain the vulnerabilities of the newly emerged Romania's regional system of alliances. It's important to mention that the overall regional equation lacked a comprehensive operational vision to allow a concerted action among the existing alliances in case of a major aggression against a regional member country. Moreover, except the alliance with Poland, no other regional scheme was committed to help Romania in the event of a conflict with Soviet Union, although this was identified as the main source of danger against Romania's security. Due to the complicated puzzle of regional hostilities and competing agendas, Romania found itself in an awkward situation. Two of its main allies, Poland and Czechoslovakia, regarded one another with an instinctive and deep-rooted hostility making any effort to generate a unified

regional front difficult to achieve. The Czechs set their hopes on Russia whom the Poles and Romanians particularly feared. Poland felt historically closed to Hungary, identified by Czechoslovakia and Romania as a major source of regional revisionism. Therefore, Romania could count neither on Czechoslovakia's support in dealing with a possible Soviet aggression, nor on Poland to contain Hungarian aggressiveness. Even more important is the fact that Poland, looking to strengthen its good relations with Hungary, did not ratify the Trianon Treaty which settled Transylvania's allegiance to Romania (Mares, 2010: 41, 55-58). Within this paradigm, Romania found itself in an unusual situation since the only ally that it could count upon to contain the Soviet threat was a country with an ambiguous position towards Romania's Western border.

Also, the Romanian-Polish treaty was not designed, due to Romania's opposition, to be applied *erga omnes* (although Poland pledged for such an approach). Therefore, Warsaw and Bucharest failed to harmonize their security alignment towards Germany (Poland's interest) and Hungary (Romania's interest).

Also, at the level of Little Entente, one can notice a lack of regional solidarity as regards the strategic imperatives of the member countries. Each of the members of the Little Entente shared different views regarding the main source of insecurity: in case of Romania, the Soviet Union was the main threat; Czechoslovakia looked at Germany while Yugoslavia had to deal with Italy's ambitions in the Balkan region. Since Romania's main priority was to contain the Soviet threat and the Hungarian revisionism, Bucharest acknowledged that a moderate relation with Germany would be helpful in both cases. Given this complicated geography of hostilities, the Little Entente did not consider any joint effort to contain the threatening great powers, since Yugoslavia and Czechoslovakia were not willing to get involved in a war with the Soviet Russia, while Romania remained reluctant to provoke the German apprehensions.

Within the Balkan Entente, the strategic algorithm among the member countries developed in similar parameters. The member countries carefully avoided provoking in any

way the big regional players and this was to greatly diminish the efficiency of the alliance. It is revealing the position of Greece which made clear that it will not be involved in a war with the big powers from outside the Balkan region (Ionescu, 1993:48-49). Following a similar logic, Turkey required a special amendment to the Athens Treaty stating its refusal to engage in any act against the Soviet Union⁵. It's worth mentioning that Turkey's initial reluctance to join the Balkan Entente was partly motivated by the tense Romanian-Soviet relations and the fear that this potential dispute could have dragged Turkey into a war with Russia. (Campus, 1972: 14-15). Following this logic, any potential support from Greece and Turkey in case of a Soviet aggressive move against Romania was highly unlikely (as confirmed by the events of June 1940 when Greece and Turkey avoided any involvement in supporting Romania when confronting with the Soviet ultimatum against Bessarabia).

A major weakness of Romania's regional strategy was the lack of a firm Western defense commitment, since the treaty with France of 1926 guaranteed no military support to Romania in case of an aggression from its revisionist neighbors. The rapprochement policy launched by France towards the Soviets in the mid '30s was a revealing proof of how the great power dynamics suppress the interests and strategic imperatives of the small regional players.

For Romania's security, the system of alliances generated a paradox: it provided no support against the main Soviet threat (except the treaty with Poland) but it complicated the country's posture towards the main regional powers, Germany and Italy, with whom Romania had no direct issue in dispute. As a result, in the complicated power game emerged in Central Europe (between Germany, France and Soviet Union) and in the Balkan region (between France, Italy and Germany), Romania's participation in the regional alliances (to some extent) reduced its ability of maneuver within the changing great powers geopolitical dynamics.

In fact, the success of the newly emerged Eastern European security geography was to depend on two important assumptions: the

willingness of the Western powers to stay involved in shaping the regional game and the commitments of the revisionist powers to comply with the rules settled by the new Versailles systemic configuration. Both failed and the consequences have dramatically affected the regional security map of Central-Eastern Europe. As a result, Romania and its regional allies had to identify their own distinct strategies of survival and shape distinct agendas of managing their strategic posture towards the main systemic players.

The disintegration of the regional system of alliances

The evolution of the regional alliances could not escape from or prevent the great power geopolitics. A series of dynamics emerged in 1933 – the failure of the disarmament conference in Geneva, Germany's withdrawal from the League of Nations and the launching of its internal re-armament program – generated centrifugal moves among the members of the regional alliances.

The rapid change of the international power configuration pushed the regional allies to look for security alternatives following their own security imperatives, even against the interests of the other alliance partners. On January 26, 1934, Poland, seeking to balance between Germany and Soviet Union and to use their rivalries as to reach a larger space of maneuver, signed the non-aggression treaty with Germany. On May 16, 1935, as a consequence of Soviet alliance with France, Czechoslovakia signed the treaty of mutual assistance with Soviet Union being stipulated, however, that the treaty would go into force only if France will provide assistance to the victim of aggression.

Due to its growing vulnerability at the Eastern border (generated by the French rapprochement with the Soviets and the emergence of the Paris-Prague-Moscow triangle) and facing an assertive Germany, Romania sought to diversify its options as to remain connected to the great power game and in the same time struggling to enlarge its network of regional allies.

As a possible direction of action, starting by '34, Bucharest attempted to open a diplomatic channel to Moscow. One of the most

preeminent supporters of this course was the Romanian minister of Foreign Affairs, Nicolae Titulescu. Under his direct supervision, bilateral Romanian-Soviet negotiations were held between 1934 and 1936. Titulescu's plan followed two main goals: to find a compromise on the disputed territory of Bessarabia and to conclude a mutual defense assistance treaty with Moscow. In this logic, it was assumed that, once the Eastern border would be recognized, Romania could join the Paris-Moscow-Prague triangle and generate a powerful deterrent against German expansion towards Eastern Europe. Titulescu explained the rationales behind his diplomatic vision showing that "a mutual assistance treaty with Moscow is necessary and useful in case that either Germany would start a war against the Soviet Union, or the two countries would reach an agreement. Moreover, the Romanian-Soviet treaty needs to be concluded at the right time, otherwise the German-Soviet rapprochement will be made without us, hence against us. As I said, the Soviet-German rapprochement must find us as allies of the Soviet Union" (Titulescu, 1992: 39)⁶. Despite Titulescu's efforts (on July

Nicolae Titulescu

1936 he signed a preliminary agreement with the Soviet Foreign Minister Litvinov), the Soviet Russia refused to recognize Bessarabia's allegiance to Romania. Moreover, the idea of a pact of mutual assistance with Moscow raised tough reactions in Warsaw which was afraid that Titulescu's line, once implemented, would have left it alone facing the Soviet threat (Mares, 2010: 55). If Romania's diplomacy towards Moscow raised serious tensions between Warsaw and Bucharest, Poland's rapprochement tendency regarding Germany increased Romania's discontent towards its ally. Nevertheless, the removal of Nicolae Titulescu put an end to Romania's diplomatic demarches to settle the Bessarabia dispute leaving Romania to manage carefully between Germany and the Western powers as the only possible option to preserve its security.

Titulescu's diplomatic plan also lacked full political support in Bucharest, where the Romanian King Carol II rather preferred a different orientation. According to his approach, Romania should accommodate Germany, with whom there was no territorial dispute, without putting into discussion Romania's security alliance with the West.

Even since the Nazi party came to power in 1933, Bucharest understood the likely impact of this event on the future Germany's strategic posture. As the Romanian minister in Berlin rightly observed, "the international treaties... are of no importance for Germany who remains obsessed with the idea of a future war and is making preparations in this direction" (Popisteanu, 1971: 104). However, assuming that Germany's main priority was to expand its economic market, Bucharest developed its own political calculus starting from the premises that the German potential assertiveness could be managed by using the *economic card*, meaning to accept economic concessions in exchange of political gains (especially important to secure the German benevolence as a counterweight against the Soviet Union and as a moderating force towards the Hungarian claims over Transylvania).

Moreover, the alliance with the West and the system of regional alliances were considered as a powerful "security umbrella" that would deter Germany from any revisionist at-

tempt. It was obvious that Germany did not share the Romanian strategic thinking. Given its rich economic resources – as the second European oil supplier – Romania became a strategic target for Berlin's economic expansionist agenda. Nevertheless, the German interest for Romania exceeded the economic dimension. The "charm offensive" launched by the new Reich starting by '34-'35⁷, seeking to convince the Romanian leadership that Germany had no intention to create territorial troubles against Romania was double motivated: economically – to shore up its influence within the Romanian economy and politically – to use the economic instrument as to detach Romania from the French-backed system of alliances as to create a breach within de Western defense shield in Eastern Europe (in such a way the revision of the borders could have been possible and easier to accomplish).

The German occupation of Rhineland in March 1936 and the inability of the Western powers to oppose Germany highly complicated the regional power equation. This was to have direct consequences over the developments emerged inside the Balkan region with a special focus on Yugoslavia. In an attempt to soften up the German expansion towards Balkans and ease the Bulgarian revisionist challenge, Belgrade decided to adopt an accommodationist policy – the so-called "Stojadinovic line" – by concluding treaties with Italy (March 25, 1937) and Bulgaria (January 24, 1937). The course pursued by Belgrade seriously affected the military activities within both regional alliances that it was part of and weaken their internal cohesion. Despite Belgrade's attempts to assure its allies, it was obvious that the Bulgarian-Yugoslavian treaty seriously questioned Yugoslavia's defense commitments within both the Little Entente and Balkan Entente. Given the new developments, during the meeting of the Permanent Council of Little Entente held in Sinaia, on August 30-31, 1937, Romania supported the development of a more active diplomacy to search for a compromise with the regional revisionist powers: Austria, Bulgaria and Hungary (Calafeteanu, 2003: 299).

The year of 1938 was marked by the renewed German assertiveness and marked a turning point that profoundly changed the

overall evolution of the military and security regional landscape. On March 1938, Germany occupied Austria and generated a new shift in the European power configuration. Simultaneously, Berlin raised the issue of Sudetenland and for the first time a member country of the system of regional alliances – Czechoslovakia – became a target of Germany's aggression. Romania had to manage a complicated dynamic between the defense needs of its ally from the Little Entente, the treaty provisions with Poland, the unsolved dispute with the Soviet Union and the German growing economic and political pressures. Against this background, Romania had to make a difficult choice since the potential activation of the French-Soviet and Soviet-Czechoslovakian pacts to help its ally Czechoslovakia would have required Romania's decision to accept the transit of the Soviet troops on its territory (Ionescu, 2014: 210). Both the Romanian and Polish governments were particularly distrustful of Soviet Russia and therefore unwilling to grant the Red Army the right of passage. According to some documentary evidences, Romania chose, however, to play a double game as revealed by the discussion between the Romanian minister of Foreign Affairs, Nicolae Petrescu-Comnen, and his Czech counterpart, Kamil Krofta, on August 1938: officially any arrangement for the Soviet transit would be rejected, but unofficially Bucharest "will close its eyes" if necessary (Hilgruber, 1994: 54-55; Ionescu, 2014: 210-212). Yugoslavia was also under strong pressures, especially after the dramatic strategic shift generated by the German occupation of Austria. Surrounded by Germany and Italy, Belgrade completely lost its space of maneuver and any support for its ally from the Little Entente became illusory. By the summer of 1938, it was obvious that the European map was changing. As a result, new efforts were made at the level of the Little Entente and Balkan Entente to accommodate the two regional revisionist states, Bulgaria and Hungary. On July 31, 1938, the Balkan Entente signed in Salonic the non-aggression agreement with Bulgaria (Moisuc, 1996: 713-714). Hungary was invited to attend the Little Entente Council at Bled, Yugoslavia in August 1938, but a compromise could not be reached to harmonize their positions.

The Munich agreement of September 1938 and the conciliatory policy adopted by the Western powers to accommodate the German geopolitical demands pushed the entire region in a state of "strategic chaos" and made the Little Entente strategically irrelevant. However, Romania adopted throughout the crisis a fair conduct towards its Czechoslovakian ally. The most revealing episode regards the proposal addressed to Romania by the minister of Foreign Affairs of Poland, Joseph Beck, to participate in the partition of Czechoslovakia and size part of Transcarpathia⁸. The Romanian King Carol II turned off the Polish initiative and tried, unsuccessfully, to moderate the aggressive intentions of Warsaw against its neighbor.

Within the Romanian political establishment, the new geopolitical dynamics generated increased anxieties especially regarding the stability of the Western border. In this context, on April 22, 1938, Hitler confirmed to Radu Djuvara, the new Romanian minister in Berlin, that Germany "considers its frontiers with Yugoslavia and Hungary as settled" and it has no territorial claim whatsoever in the Balkans. So that, Germany's main objective regards economic interests in the area" (Hilgruber, 1994: 51-52). One can assume that the main rationale behind Hitler's "generosity" was, in fact, connected to Germany's economic agenda, particularly important being to secure the oil deliveries and get further advantageous economic deals with Romania by preventing a possible destabilization of the country.

Nevertheless, the Munich deal between the Western powers and Germany dramatically diminished Romania's strategic options and left it in a deep security vacuum. It became obvious that the evolution of the systemic order was going to be settled through the exclusive game of the great powers. The main question was how Romania was to position itself in the new European strategic equation.

The growing tendency of the Western powers to accommodate Germany and the encouraging messages sent from Berlin, prompted some voices within the Romanian political establishment to advocate for a closer relation with Germany. As the Romanian statesman, Octavian Goga, put it: "The United Roma-

nia could be created only by fighting against Vienna, but it cannot be preserved without Berlin's support" (Otu, 2006: 29). Nevertheless, such a hypothesis was considered only as a complementary option to the Western alliance, since no political leader could afford to seriously question Romania's firm commitment to the Western alliance.

Facing a resurgent Germany from the West, a potential Soviet threat from the East and an increased regional isolation, Bucharest sought to play a complicated game between Germany and the West. This is why a major concern in Bucharest was to moderate the German growing economic demands being afraid that it could easily turn its economic influence into a political control over the country. In such a scenario, Bucharest's Western orientation would have become highly vulnerable to Germany's maneuvers. The visit paid by King Carol II to London, Paris and Berghof (November 1938) provided a gloomy picture regarding the ambiguous security commitments of the Western powers towards Romania and their intentions to help it balance the German economic influence. Yet, King Carol II rejected Hitler's offer to guarantee the integrity of borders in exchange of Romania's willingness to switch the alliances.

By early 1939, Germany increased its pressures to conclude an economic agreement with Romania. Facing a dramatic change of the regional security map following the occupation of Czechoslovakia (March 15, 1939), the only option left for Romania was to accept to sign the economic treaty (March 23, 1939) granting Germany a dominant voice in its economic affairs. As to understand Romania's strategic approach, it's interesting to mention how the prime-minister Armand Călinescu motivated the conclusion of the Romanian-German economic treaty: "I must say that I have accepted the economic agreement with Germany because I wanted to save time and gain some economic advantages, not to get closer politically to Germany" (Otu, 2006: 30). The idea was to convince France and Great Britain that Romania remained their ally and the relation with Germany answered to a specific geopolitical context. The fact that Romania signed shortly a broad economic treaty with France

reveals the thinking algorithm in Bucharest. Moreover, following complicated diplomatic maneuvers ('Vasile Tilea' case), Romania convinced Great Britain and France to provide unilaterally, on April 13, 1939, security guarantees to the Kingdom of Romania (Scurtu, 2000: 111-114). Similar guarantees were provided to Greece, particularly important after Italy had occupied Albania in early April 1939. Important to mention the duplicitous attitude of Polish foreign minister, Joseph Beck, who asked Great Britain to be more cautious in providing security guarantees to Romania since such an action would drive Hungary even closer towards Germany. Nevertheless, at this point, the existing regional alliances were disintegrating, the whole Central and Southeastern Europe being turned into a decisive playground of a major systemic competition. The security commitments provided by the Western powers came too late and they could not change any more the course of the events that were to settle the fate of the whole Eastern Europe.

The collapse of regional security architecture

The German-Soviet Pact of August 1939 and the outbreak of the war completely changed Romania's entire security architecture. Its security strategy based on keeping an ambivalent position towards Germany as to preserve its Western alliance collapsed. Romania found itself alone between the two totalitarian hegemones – both hostile to Romania – which had already agreed to shape the territorial systemic order according to their strategic imperatives and geopolitical interests.

On August 25, 1939, Bucharest informed Warsaw that, in case of a conflict with Germany, it will keep neutrality⁹. Romania reiterated its "peaceful position" immediately after France and Great Britain submitted their war declarations to Germany on September 3, 1939. On September 6, 1939, the Crown Council decided to proclaim the neutrality of Romania. (Mamina, 1997: 176-188). One week later, an official declaration was sent to Hermann Göring informing him about Bucharest's decision. A similar declaration was submitted to Moscow on September 21, 1939¹⁰.

Within this configuration, the Romanian government tried to secure its borders and avoid being dragged into a war by operationalizing the Balkan bloc of neutral countries and by seeking, unsuccessfully, to reach a non-aggression treaty with the Soviets using the Turkish channel. The Romanian idea of establishing a block of neutrals in the Balkan region failed due to the opposition of the revisionist powers. When the Soviet troops advanced into Poland, the Polish government acknowledged that Romania was in fact unable to honor any of its treaty obligations and it did not call for the help of its ally. Moreover, on December 14, 1939, London informed the Romanian government, who wanted to know if the French-British guarantees will be applied *erga omnes*, that the British defense guarantees would come into effect, in case of a Soviet attack, only if Turkey would provide immediate support to Bucharest and Italy will not raise any opposition (Hillgruber, 1994:96-97). This declaration lacked any practical value since Turkey reiterated categorically, on the occasion of the conclusion of its treaty with Great Britain and France on October 19, 1939, its opposition regarding a possible involvement in an action against the Soviet Union. In the same time, Turkey and Yugoslavia have tried to use their *good offices*, during the last meeting of the Balkan Entente (Belgrade, 2-4 February 1940) to convince Romania to be "more sympathetic" towards the Hungarian territorial claims. The idea was categorically rejected by Bucharest motivating that such a behavior would open the door to revisionism throughout the region.

It was the defeat of France which completely changed the regional power configuration and had a dramatic impact on Bucharest's strategic thinking, leading to a radical shift of its political orientation. Facing growing Soviet assertiveness on its Eastern border, on May 29, 1940, the King Carol II decided, during a meeting with his ministers¹¹, to shift the foreign policy orientation towards a close rapprochement with Germany, perceived as the only power able to deter the Soviets. During the meeting it was decided that Romania will adopt the status of non-belligerence. Yet, Bucharest's new course could not change the great power game between Moscow and Berlin. It was also obvi-

ous that Romania could not count any more on its allies from the Balkan Entente for support. When the Romanian government received the Soviet ultimatum, on June 26, 1940, to "return" Bessarabia and "transfer" Northern Bukovina to the Soviet Union, Greece and Yugoslavia asked Romania to accept it and not to disturb regional peace through military resistance. On June 27, 1940, the Crown Council decided to accept the Soviet terms and in the same day King Carol II asked Hitler to guarantee the territorial frontiers and to send a German military mission to protect the country against the Soviet threat. On November 22, 1940, General Ion Antonescu, the head of state since September 1940, signed the allegiance to the Tripartite Pact, event which marked Romania's entry into the alliance with Germany. At that point, the Kingdom of Romania had already lost Bessarabia and Bukovina (June 1940), Transylvania (August 1940) and Dobruja (September 1940) and was struggling to avoid a complete disintegration of the country.

A few conclusions

The system of regional alliances forged by Romania tried to build a workable security system to defend its own national interests. In a general perspective, the network of political and military alliances concluded by Romania during the '20-'30s had an exclusive self-defense character aiming at preserving the regional status-quo and overcome the deep insecurity of its borders. The new regional map was an integral part of the Versailles systemic order and it was to play an important role in the general geopolitical dynamics aiming at shaping a new balance of power in Europe. However, since the beginning, the new systemic configuration attempted by Bucharest was vulnerable to both the potential internal dynamics of the member countries and the evolution of hegemonic power game that the small Eastern European countries could not influence or contain by themselves.

The overall security strategy built by Bucharest during the inter-war years was based on the assumption that the Western powers will support the regional status-quo of Central and Eastern Europe against the potential sources of insecurity coming from the revisionist coun-

tries (Hungary, Bulgaria, Albania) and will prevent the region turning into a battlefield of the hegemonic ambitions of the defeated regional powers – Germany and the Soviet Russia.

This strong belief shaped Bucharest's typology of behavior despite the trends emerged starting by the early '30s that showed growing German interests towards the Central and Eastern Europe, the consolidation of the strategic posture of USSR which started to recover its key geopolitical role and an increasing passive attitude of the Western powers willing, if necessary, to make certain "sacrifices" in the East as to preserve the security in the West.

In reality, Romania's security as well as the entire system of regional alliances depended upon the credibility of the Western powers and their assumed commitment towards their Eastern allies. After the Treaty of Locarno and the remilitarization of Rhineland, France lost its great power prestige and credibility. As a result, the Central and Eastern Europe became an arena of hegemonic competition of systemic dimension and this allowed the great revisionist actors to generate lines of hostility among the regional allies. Left without credible Western defense commitments, the small regional countries became highly vulnerable to the geopolitical maneuvers and this was to highly affect the cohesion of the entire region.

In a general perspective, one can assume that the Romanian decision makers accurately evaluated the international dynamics and their impact on Romania's security posture. Nevertheless, Romania, as a status-quo power with a security agenda focused on preserving its territorial integrity had limited strategic options and a weak potential to manage the geopolitical configuration around its borders. Moreover, given its strategic location and rich natural resources (especially oil and cereals), it became a major strategic stake in the battle for systemic influence among the big players of the international scene.

It was obvious that Romania did not have the potential to play between Germany and the West. Germany accepted Bucharest's ambivalent policy because it needed Romanian resources and the country's political predictability was important as to accomplish its military agenda in the West and avoid "surprises" that

could force it to split its forces on two fronts or being left without oil supplies crucially important for its war machine. After the defeat of France, any illusion of "strategic freedom" was lost, the only option left being to choose between Soviet Union and Germany. Either way, Romania's role was to be subordinated to the dominant might of the hegemon. The choice of joining Germany was not an option, but a tactic of survival imposed by the dynamics of the hegemonic power competition following the Western military collapse.

Romania's overall strategy posture between 1919 and 1940 reveals the profound systemic constraints that highly impacted upon and defined the role of a small country and its typology of behavior within the systemic power competition. As a small size country, located in the clashing zone of the European hegemonic powers – Germany and Russia –, with a weak military potential, surrounded by small and weak regional allies that put their national interests above the general interests of the region, and with Western allies unwilling or unable to help, Romania's only chance of survival depended on the dynamic of the great power game that it could not control or influence by itself.

It's an open question in what extent Romania could have negotiated a better deal with Germany in order to safeguard its territorial integrity by using the German vital interest to have a safe access to the Romanian oil fields. It's also difficult to predict Germany's behavior in case that Romania would have decided to resist militarily against the Soviet Union in June 1940 risking to turn the country into a battlefield and threatening the safety oil supplies crucially important for the German war machine.

It's likely that regardless the course of action that Bucharest could have adopted, it could not change in any way the great power geopolitical game so that the only two options left in 1940 being either to save as much as possible of its territory or to end up being occupied and completely disintegrated. Romania chose the first option that resulted in its "forced" allegiance to the German military camp, an alternative that the Romanian leadership struggled to avoid throughout the inter-war period.

NOTES

¹ Starting by 1921, Romania's diplomatic initiatives received a significant impetus once the idea of a possible Habsburg restoration started to flow within some chancelleries beginning by 1921 and this was to provide the glue linking the countries which shared similar concerns as regards the revival of the former Habsburg imperial design and the Hungarian revisionism (Benes, 1922; Crampton, 1997: 37).

² The bilateral Romanian-Polish convention was renewed in 1926 and 1931.

³ Archives of the Ministry of Foreign Affairs (AMAE), Fond Balkan Entente, Text of the Treaty of Athens, vol. 16, f. 169.

⁴ AMAE, Fond Balkan Entente, The military convention between Greece, Yugoslavia, Turkey and Romania, vol. 36, f. 270-279.

⁵ AMAE, Fond Balkan Entente, The secret annex to the Balkan Entente Pact, vol. 13, f. 166.

⁶ Besides the fact that Titulescu rightly predicted the potential German-Soviet dynamics and their impact over Romania, he in fact intended to pursue a more ambitious European agenda. Titulescu sought to prevent a return to "Bismarck policy", meaning the German-Soviet friendship and therefore his diplomacy aimed at bringing the Soviet Union as part of the French-backed collective security system and to turn it into an important pillar of the regional balance of power to deter Germany. Moreover, Titulescu pledged for an alliance between France, Little Entente and Soviet Russia so that a mutual assistance pact between Paris and Moscow, with Romania as a "vital link", was to be a key component in the new imagined security architecture (Rebecca Haynes, 2000: 4).

⁷ As part of this offensive, the German leadership sought to assure Bucharest that it has no intention to support the Hungarian revisionism against

Romania. In this regard, in 1935 Germany proposed to King Carol II a Treaty of friendship between Bucharest and Berlin as to include the recognition of the Romanian borders, together with a large scale bilateral commercial treaty. Similar assurances were also given to Romanian officials by Hermann Göring as happened during the meeting with the Romanian political leader, Gheorghe Brătianu, on November 16, 1936 (Hilgruber, 1994: 44).

⁸ Joseph Beck raised for the first time this issue during the discussions held in Galați with the Romanian King Carol II and the minister of Foreign Affairs Nicolae Petrescu-Comnen on October 19, 1938.

⁹ Despite strong pressures from the Soviet Union and Germany, starting by September 17, 1939, the Romanian government supported its ally by offering asylum to the Polish leadership (the president, members of government, the chief of General Staff) and to all Polish civilians and military who could make it across the border. Around 100.000 persons fled to Romania. Mostly of the Polish Armed Forces later left Romania and made their way to the west to continue the resistance against Germany.

¹⁰ It is assumed that Romania attempted to play the decision of neutrality as a strategy to "buy" time until the Western powers would consolidate their positions and push back the German military offensive. Following this logic, Romania could join war at a decisive moment and this was to increase its chances to play an important role in future peace negotiations. The rationale behind Bucharest's political thinking was twofold: the West will defeat Germany and the war will be short-lived.

¹¹ The decision of establishing close relations with Germany was taken during a meeting between King Carol II, the prime-minister Gheorghe Tătărescu, the minister of Foreign Affairs, Grigore Gafencu and the Minister of the Court, Ernest Urdăreanu.